

Fundamentals, Limitations and Promising Future of Excitonic Solar Cell

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Abstract

Mesoporous TiO₂ based excitonic solar cell (EXSC) has promising future for the unique properties new sensitizer and solid state electrolyte materials. The advanced materials has the capacity to contribute the important role such as multi-exciton generation (MEG), free-carrier transport and proper collection on electrode for enhanced stabilized efficiency in TiO₂ based solar cell. CH₃NH₃PbX₃ (X = Br, I) based solid-state perovskites can replace dye and act as sensitizers. Spiro-MeOTAD acts as solid-state electrolyte that can replace highly degradable, low stable and high cost liquid electrolyte materials. The proper understanding about the limitations of different kinds of solar cell materials in terms of materials properties, physibility in the device and cost price is crucial for further forward movement to overcome the milestone. In this paper, novel properties of multifunctional materials, basic architecture and fundamentals of EXSC, limitations, promising active materials for further improvement of device performance, and future prospective will be discussed.

Keywords: Mesoporous TiO₂, Solid-State Electrolyte, MEG, Hole Transporting Material, PV-Performance.

1. Introduction

A typical Excitonic Solar Cell (EXSC) consists of three major components: Electrodes, buffer layer and active materials (hole and electron transporting layers). The device converts light energy directly into electric power without any permanent change in stoichiometry of the chemicals. To understand the basics of photoinduced charge transfer and excitonic state, enormous research is going on heterostructure, quantum well, superlattice, quantum well, nanowires and quantum dots¹⁻⁵.

Mesoporous TiO₂ surrounded by organic dye/quantum-dot with proper surface functionalized structure plays crucial role for exciton generation, instant charge separation between TiO₂ and QD/organic semiconducting materials within the excitonic solar cell architecture. Low dimensional semiconducting materials in the form of nanostructure can be effective for proper bandgap matching via proper band-bending and high electronic mobility for photo-generated electron collection due to large contact area. The photo-generated voltage mainly depends on band bending mechanism.

For carrier transport electron transporting materials (ETM) as well as hole transporting materials have significant role to achieve better photovoltaic performance. In this context, the materials with greater electron affinity act as electron transporting material (ETM) and especially conducting polymers having lower ionization potential used as the hole transport material (HTM) reported somewhere⁶. Detailed balance of power conversion efficiency limit for an ideal *p-n* junction solar cell is described by Shockley and Queisser limit by which new photovoltaic technologies are compared. Photovoltaic measurements are performed under ideal illumination condition with AM 1.5G light source having surface temperature of 6000 K where light absorption and scattering in the atmosphere has been taken into account. In solar photovoltaics (PVs) conventional light-absorbing materials like Si, GaAs, CIGS compound etc. have been studied for last half-century.

Theoretical Shockley-Queisser (SQ) limit is approximately 33% for single-junction silicon ($E_g=1.1\text{eV}$) based cell, and the same is 44% for a multi-junction tandem solar cell

under normal sunlight⁴. On the other hand, the same theoretical limit is 68.7% for single junction cell and 86.8% for multijunction solar cell under concentrated sunlight⁵. Main objective is to developing novel light absorbers (many unexplored materials) that potentially offer efficiency beyond theoretical SQ limit as well as stability, and cost of PVs. Very recently hot-carrier harvesting, will be one of the main challenge of the next-generation PV research to cross theoretical SQ limit.

In this review article, author has highlighted the summary of device architecture, working mechanism, current status, and limitations of modern Excitonic solar cell. The key realizing goal is to understand the hot carrier harvesting through different unexplored materials to overcome Shockley-Queisser efficiency limit.

1. Device Architecture and Basics of Excitonic Solar Cell

Solar cells can be broadly classified into two distinct categories: (i) Conventional p-n junctions and (ii) Excitonic solar cells.

In conventional p-n junction solar cell, light is absorbed in the active layer across p-n junction and creates photo generated electron-hole pair across the junction. Photo-generated 'electrons' will be collected in n-side and 'hole' will be collected in p-side under illumination condition. Potential difference is developed across the active layer of p-n junction diode and hence light energy is converted into electrical power.

On the other hand, excitonic solar cells include dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSC) and organic photovoltaics (OPV), organic-inorganic hybrid solar cell, Quantum dot solar cell (QDSC) and perovskite based solar cell where sun's light energy is harvested through organic-dye, polymer, quantum dot or perovskite materials etc to generate electricity. In these new generation solar cells electro-statically bound electron-hole pair (exciton) dissociates into free charge carriers across a heterointerface under illumination condition. Excitonic solar cells are very much attractive for few distinct promising characteristics like very low-cost due to very thin architecture, light-weight, flexible and portable size. Continuous research is going on to upgrade power conversion efficiency and device stability as well as to realize their full potential for realistic solution of energy crisis. Multiple exciton generation (MEG) is one of the emerging concepts of the combination of incident photon energy and semiconductor band gap to increase nanomaterials based excitonic solar cells efficiency beyond the SQ-limit.

The limiting values for $J_{0,SQ}$ according to the SQ model were calculated using the Shockley diode equation for a solar cell under illumination, assuming an ideal diode:

$$J = J_{sc} - J_0 \left(\exp \left[\frac{qV}{\eta k_B T} \right] - 1 \right) \text{ where, at } V = V_{oc}, J = 0 \text{ and } J_0 = J_{sc} \left(\exp \left[\frac{qV}{\eta k_B T} \right] - 1 \right)^{-1}$$

With the help of above equations, for each bandgap will be J_{sc} and V_{oc} known, and corresponding SQ- J_0 values can be obtained. The simulated $J_{0,exp}$ value using first-order analysis (series and shunt losses ignored) for each solar cell can be compared with experimental V_{oc} and J_{sc} values with standard photovoltaic measurement conditions (AM1.5G spectrum, 1000 W/m², 25 °C).

Based on similar Shockley-Queisser model, the theoretical efficiency limit for two-layer, three-layer and a theoretical infinity-layer cell has been reported as 42%, 49% and 68% respectively under non-concentrated sunlight measurement condition. In that analysis photon absorption, and re-emission with different frequencies within the multi-layered structure has been taken into consideration.

In EXSCs the photon (light) energy transformation into electrical energy takes place via three basic steps: (1) Photon absorption and exciton formation, (2) Charge separation or exciton dissociation and (3) Charge transport.

Fig.1-The structure and working principle of EXSC

Exciton generation, migration, and dissociation are key parameters for controlling many organic optoelectronic devices performances. Efficient MEG occurs through slow cooling process by energetic hot carriers. Hot carriers are formed due to enhanced electrostatic interaction and reduction of density of states under strong quantum confinement via inverse Auger transition with lifetime 90 fs.

Free carriers generation to carrier transport to achieve efficient photocurrent occurs through exciton dissociation at the interface, followed by polaron generation, recombination and transport (in many organic photovoltaic devices). Exciton diffusion that plays key role for suitable energy transfer depends on exciton diffusion length (L_D) ($=(D\tau)^{1/2}$, where D be the exciton diffusion co-efficient and τ be exciton lifetime) as well as its lifetime (τ).

Grover and Silbey⁷ reported the direct calculation of exciton diffusion coefficient from the equations of motion for the microscopic exciton density. The exciton diffusion length of most classical organic semiconductors belongs to 5-20 nm and Exciton diffusion length varies from material to material as well as with materials composition. L_D is the maximum limits of the donor and acceptor impurity size within the active layer of the exciton based solar cell.

L_D values can be estimated by measuring photoluminescence of the sensitizer and it is the function of active layer thickness and sensitizer layer concentration (for singlet and triplet excitonic states) reported elsewhere [Journal of Material Chemistry C (Issue 19, 2019, DOI <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9TC00686A>)]. It has been reported that for Injection layer having diffusion length around 29.8nm, singlet L_D values are 15.2nm and 16.6nm for the fluorophores tris-(8-hydroxyquinoline) aluminum (Alq_3)(transport layer) and bis-(8-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline)-(4-phenylphenoxy) aluminum (BAIq) (Sensitizer layer) respectively.

In that case, Tris [2-phenylpyridinato-C2, N] iridium(III) ($\text{Ir}(\text{ppy})_3$) is used as phosphorescent singlet exciton injector layer ($E_T = 2.4$ eV). Triplets are injected into nano-particle domain and those migrate through the layer may undergo energy transfer to a sensitizer layer. Platinum octaethylporphyrin (PtOEP , $E_T = 1.9$ eV) is used as sensitizer layer in exciton based solar cell.

The donor and the acceptor semiconductors are in a direct physical contact in hybrid solar cell (HSC) and therefore exciton dissociation takes place efficiently at the interfaces.

Thus, one of the active materials may can play the following dual functions (i) light-harvesting and (ii) charge carrier (hole or electron) transport.

In Dye sensitized solar cell (DSSC), dye is adsorbed on the nanostructured semiconductor oxide surface (usually TiO_2 nanoparticles), and plays active role for light absorption. Upon excitation an electron is injected into the conduction band oxide material and transported through the nanoparticle network. The charge carriers' separation between the light-absorber material (Dye) and the charge carrier material in DSSC is almost similar to excitonic based new generation solar cells. Here exciton dissociation mechanism seems to be the key to their higher efficiency and longer lifetime.

2. Active Materials

Different multifunctional materials play active role in light-harvesting and charge transport mechanism in EXSC. The power conversion efficiency as well as the device stability of EXSCs are controlled by the versatile characteristics of transparent conducting substrate (TCO) materials, nanocrystalline semiconductor oxide film as buffer layer, Organic/QD materials as sensitizers, electrolytes and counter electrodes. Liquid electrolytes must be replaced by Solid based materials to improve better carrier transport in EXSCs to achieve enhanced stabilized efficiency.

Based on different categories of semiconductor material, Excitonic solar cell (EXSCs) can be classified into three general categories organic solar cell (OSCs), Organic-Inorganic hybrid solar cell (HSCs) and dye-sensitized solar cell (DSSCs). In OSCs, p-type and n-type organic semiconducting materials, for example the blend between two conducting organic polymers or a mixture between C_{60} derivative and a conjugated polymer are used for device fabrication. In the case of HSC, the combination of inorganic semiconductor (*e.g.* CdSe, TiO_2)(at least –one phase) and a conducting organic polymer are used for device fabrication. But, DSSCs is one of the examples of EXSC, and have some limitations due to the presence of a liquid electrolyte. The used In EXSCs, inorganic materials in the form of nano-particles, nanorods, tetrapods, nanosheets etc are used for many unique solutions.

There are many inorganic semiconducting oxide materials such as TiO_2 , Nb_2O_5 , ZnO, SnO_2 , CeO_2 or CeO_2 - TiO_2 are used as promising materials for EXSCs and inorganic semiconductors like CdSe, copper indium disulfide (CuInS_2), CuInSe_2 and CuInTe_2 , PbS, GsAs, PbSe, or HgTe nanocrystals are used in organic-inorganic hybrid solar cell (HSCs). Nanostructured ZnO has become promising candidate due to its' easy and low-cost synthesis techniques and its multifunctional properties.

Another important active material in EXSC is electrolyte that can be roughly divided into three categories based on its physical state: liquid electrolyte, quasi-solid electrolyte, and solid-state electrolyte.

Liquid electrolytes

A liquid electrolyte consists of a solvent, a redox couple and additives. An ionic liquid-based electrolyte is most exciting charge mediators in practical EXSCs applications.

Most common liquid electrolytes used in EXSC based solar cells are the redox couple, solvent, acrylonitrile (AcN), ethylene carbonate (EC), propylene carbonate (PC), 3-methoxypropionitrile (MePN), and N-methylpyrrolidone (NMP), I_3^-/I^- [2], bipyridyl cobalt (III/II)-complexes⁸, $(\text{SCN})_2/\text{SCN}^-$ ⁹, $(\text{SeCN})_2/\text{SeCN}^-$ ¹⁰ etc.

Redox electrolytes are basically ionic conductors and charge transfer takes place by ionic conduction via diffusion (concentration controlled) or by migration (electric field

controlled) through oxidation-reduction cycles. Acetonitrile/Valero-nitrile electrolyte based DSSC cell shows 9.1% and 10% power conversion efficiency respectively¹¹. Different dye and electrolyte combination shows the different efficiency, latest efficiency of DSSCs attained 15% with organic dye, though it has limited commercial applications. Other types of liquid electrolytes such as ferrocene and disulfide/thiolate have been successfully used in the DSSC configuration.

In general, ionic liquids based electrolytes show record efficiency of DSSCs based solar cell, but ionic liquids are highly volatile with high leakage factor. The above mentioned factors are responsible for high evaporation rates of ionic liquids and that limits the long-term stability of such excitonic devices. Some special organic salts containing 'Cations' such as pyridinium, imidazolium, and 'Anions' from the halide or pseudohalide family^[11] belonging room temperature ionic liquids (RTIL) category can minimize the above restriction. The most commonly used ionic liquid (IL) for DSSC applications is N, N' bis-alkyl-substituted imidazolium iodides show multifunctional properties act like simultaneous iodine source and as a solvent.

Quasi-solid electrolytes

As alternative of liquid electrolyte, i.e. quasi-solid-state electrolytes Ionic liquids such as 1-propargyl-3-methylimidazolium iodide, bis(imidazolium) iodides and 1-ethyl-1-methylpyrrolidinium) and polymer gel (e.g. poly(ethylene oxide), poly(vinylidene fluoride) and polyvinyl acetate) containing redox couples are commonly used as quasi-solid-state electrolytes to overcome the volatilization and leakage problems of liquid electrolytes. However, quasi-solid-state electrolytes still suffer from solvent leakage due to their thermodynamic instability under high temperature and thus careful sealing treatments are also required¹¹.

Solid State Electrolytes

Very recently solid state electrolytes can play key role for enhanced performance and stable excitonic solar cell for large scale applications. In case of Solid state DSSC basically two types of electrolytes are used such as 'hole transporting materials' (HTM) and I_3^-/I^- redox couple as medium. In high-performance SS-EXSCs, Solid-state electrolytes offers good diffusion of HTMs for effective hole transfer into photoanode films to achieve fast electrical transport.

Mixture of liquid electrolytes with polymers, inorganic silica nanoparticles, and low molecular weight organic gelators^{12,13} is the basic material for Quasi- or solid-state electrolytes. CuI, CuBr, and CuSCN are the example of Copper based compounds for solid electrolytes (inorganic HTMs) and the above choice is due to their good conductivity reported elsewhere¹⁴. Some materials like CsSnI₃ electrolyte contributed to establish 10.2% power conversion efficiency (PCE)¹⁵, whereas Spiro-MeOTAD is much better than other types of organic HTMs¹⁶, and 15% PCE is already achieved using perovskite-based solid state electrolyte reported in 2013¹⁷.

3. Latest Status

In May 2013, Dyesol^[18] reported 11.3% power conversion efficiency of solid-state dye sensitized solar cell (ss-DSSC), on the other hand perovskites solar cell produces 15% efficiency in the same year. New two-step deposition processes are appropriate to create multi-exciton for solid-state dye solar cells. Dyesol's key DSC input materials and specially formulated 18NR-T Titania Paste as the light harvesting pigment were used during two steps cell fabrication techniques and record efficiency of 18% for a solid-state Dye Sensitized Solar Cell (ssDSSC)¹⁸ has been reported. After breakthrough investigation, perovskite solar cell

(PSCs) became very much popular in photovoltaic (PV) research and upto 22.1% power conversion efficiency (PCE) was reported in early 2016. At the same time, maximum theoretical limit in PCE of 31.4% for $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_{3-x}\text{Cl}_x$ based the PSCs was reported elsewhere¹⁹. There is enough scope for further improvement in the following cases – (i) tuning of Tin-doped indium oxide (ITO)/fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) substrate as well as metal electrode material properties, (ii) stability of perovskite photoactive material, (iii) transport properties of hole transport layer (HTL)²⁰ as well as electron transport layer (ETL) in PSC architecture^{21,22, 23}. A group of scientists from University of California, Berkeley, and Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory designed a new PSC architecture using graded bandgap materials during November, 2016 and reported an average stabilized efficiency of 18.4%, with a height of 21.7% and a peak efficiency of 26%²⁴⁻³⁰. In this aspect, semiconductors quantum dots play big role to generate multiexciton (i.e. more than one excited electron per absorbed photon instead of a single electron) at the band edge in the broad solar spectrum in case of prototype solar cells³⁰.

Fig-1: Variation of Performance Growth of Perovskite Solar Cell

In other word, singlet exciton fission process can explain multiple exciton generation mechanism. During single exciton fission, one singlet exciton splits into two triplet excitons of lower energy, that may couple with low bandgap semiconductor. In this way, MEG can help to achieve higher theoretical efficiency limit³¹ and also quantum efficiencies exceeding 100% have been reported³² for the materials like Mott insulators. In Mott insulators, excited electrons interact strongly with the remaining electrons and this coupling helps to generate multiple excitons reported elsewhere³³. To achieve maximum theoretical quantum efficiency limit, optimized composition and crystal structure of the perovskite materials can play significant role. Modeling and simulation can help to predict the optimized composition and suitable crystal structure of perovskite materials. In excitonic solar cell, the thin film synthesis mechanism, suitable HTM layer and electrode materials, interfacial engineering, encapsulation methods (multilayer encapsulation or helmet encapsulation); and the module technology can play very much important role for improved efficiency. The interface plays crucial role for the performance of excitonic solar cell in terms of multi-exciton generation, dissociation, and recombination as well as degradation mechanism³⁴. Dyesol currently introduced high purity sensitizing dyes (titania pastes) & platinum pastes, silver Inks as electrode, low volatile electrolytes, sealants for flexible and rigid devices and better performances have been reported.

4. Limitations

For the daily life application and commercial viability, efficiency and stability are the most important factors for EXSC. Following factors limit the efficiency and stability of EXSCs enlisted below: (i) conducting organic polymers have poor electronic mobility of the order typically around $10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. (ii) shorter recombination lifetime of photo-generated electron-hole pair in dye based EXSC. very fast and very fast exciton generation and recombination of 99% photo generated electron-hole pairs limits the performance of TiO_2 based DSSC, (iii) non-stabilized dark current due to poor NIR response of dyes materials, (iv) poor interface between the electrodes and active materials, (v) low volatility and high viscosity of electrolytes, (vi) Possible desorption and Photo-degradation of active materials (dye) under UV exposure, (vii) Leakage and volatilization of solvents, and (viii) Corrosion of Pt counter electrode in liquid electrolytes.

Table-1: Shockley – Queisser Limit and Experimental Evidence for different combinations in Tandem Solar Cell

Sl.No.	Tandem Materials combination	Bandgap (eV)	SQ limiting Efficiency	Record Efficiency	SQ Efficiency with Losses (%)
1.	GaInP/GaAs	1.95/1.42	40.4	32.8	34.8
2.	Perovskite/Si	1.70/1.12	44.1	29.2	35.7
3.	Perovskite/Perovskite	1.82/1.27	40.9	24.2	33.2
4.	Perovskite/CIGS	1.70/1.13	43.6	24.2	32.8
5.	GaAsP/Si	1.73/1.12	44.9	23.4	

Above table (Table-1) gives summarized information's of record efficiency limit and losses for different materials combinations in tandem solar cell architecture. Above 55% of the total absorbed solar energy can be converted into electricity and the Shockley–Queisser limit is responsible for huge losses of solar energy. SQ theoretical limit is due to below band-gap materials and hot carrier effect due to thermalization. The concepts based on hot carrier equilibration and carrier multiplication may be the possible solution to reduce dominant losses in novel solar cell. Recently hot-electron extraction (from photo-excited semiconductor nano-crystals) has been demonstrated experimentally to study the feasibility to minimize the loss mechanism in hot carrier solar cell. For the multi-exciton solar cell, singlet fission focus on the molecular analog. Quantum coherent mechanism is a process in hot carrier solar cell where photo-excited organic semiconductor (pentacene or tetracene) creates a quantum superposition of singlet exciton and multi-exciton states. This quantum superposition and the corresponding decoherence time (*i.e.*, singlet fission time) are critical to the competing dynamics of charge or energy harvesting. Graphene and related materials are the potentially ideal chromophores for hot carrier solar cells.

Conclusions

Mesoporous TiO_2 based excitonic solar cell (EXSC) has promising future for wireless society (mobile communications) remote sensing-transmitters, building management and also the road lane makers. Highest power conversion efficiency of 26% is reported in Graded Bandgap Perovskite Solar Cells. Solid-state electrolytes offers good diffusion and high conductivity for effective hole transfer in hole transporting layers in high-performance SS-EXSCs. The interface in excitonic based multilayered solar cell plays crucial role for the

performance of in terms of multi-exciton generation, dissociation, and recombination as well as degradation mechanism. The Shockley-Queisser limit in terms of power conversion efficiency can be achievable for a particular material with multiple exciton generation (MEG) capacity in nanostructure based excitonic solar cell.

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